

Magnetic and Magnetocaloric Properties of $0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ Composite

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In the present work, the magnetic and magnetocaloric properties of $0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ ($0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}/0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.1}$) composite have been investigated. Our composite $0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}/0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.1}$ has been synthesized using the solid-state reaction. X-ray diffraction (XRD) at room temperature has been used to carry out the structural properties. In order to investigate the magnetic and magnetocaloric properties of the samples, magnetization measurements dependence on temperature and magnetic field have been performed by using physical property measurement system. XRD results indicate that all our samples crystallized in the orthorhombic structure with Pnma space group. Magnetization measurements versus temperature for the composite reveal two magnetic transition temperatures associated to both manganites, which induces an enlargement of the magnetic entropy change peak. Based on Maxwell relation, the maximum magnetic entropy change ($|\Delta S_M^{max}|$) of the composite has been calculated as $1.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which corresponds to relative cooling power (RCP) about 17.8 J kg^{-1} under a magnetic field change of 5T.

1. Introduction

Perovskite manganites with the general formula $\text{A}_{1-x}\text{B}_x\text{MnO}_3$ (A = Pr, La, Nd,... and B = Ba, Sr, Ca,...) have been of large recent interest due to their electrical and magnetic properties [1-4]. This type of materials can be used in different technological applications such as colossal magneto-resistance, computer memory systems, storage devices and magnetic refrigerants [5-8]. The magnetic ground state in these materials is sensitive to variations of the Mn-O bond length and Mn-O-Mn bond angle and $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ ions [9]. The variation of ions in A and B-sites has a sensitive impact on physical properties of perovskite manganites. Also, the Mn site substitution by different elements affects the Mn-O-Mn networks and the combination of the double-exchange interaction (DE) coupled $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ ions [10, 11].

The reported magnetocaloric effect (MCE) in the manganites and the ability to control their Curie temperature by chemical substitutions opened doors for the production of new candidates of nonpolluting magnetic refrigerants in a wide temperature range. Also, MCE is becoming a promising technology to replace the conventional gas compression-expansion technique [12, 13]. The MCE can be defined as the adiabatic temperature

change (ΔT_{ad}) or the isothermal magnetic entropy change (ΔS_M) of a system due to the applied magnetic field [14]. In addition, the manganites have attracted the widest interest in aspects of theoretical and experimental researches due to their large magnetic entropy change. More than that, a large magnetic entropy change can be tuned in a large temperature range, intervening on the chemical composition of these materials, which is advantageous for magnetic refrigeration [15, 16]. Moreover, the manganites are very convenient for the synthesis routes, and their Curie temperature can be justified under various doping conditions. Therefore, the new trends have been focusing on studying the MCE of manganite composites [17, 18].

In this work, we elaborated by the solid state method at high temperature, the composite $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ composite studied their magnetic and magnetocaloric properties.

2. Results and Discussion

The powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of our samples have been recorded at room temperature. Figures 1a-b) show the refined XRD

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patterns for $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ samples, including the observed and calculated profiles as well as the difference profile. Our samples are single phase without any detectable impurity and crystallize in the orthorhombic system with a Pbnm space group [19]. After the formation of the two mother compounds, $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3$ / $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$, we prepared the composite with composition 50% of each.

Figure 1. Observed and calculated X-ray diffraction data and Rietveld refinement for **a)** $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3$ and **b)** $\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$. Vertical bars are the Bragg reflections for the space group Pnma. The difference pattern between the observed data and fits is shown at the bottom.

Figure 2 shows the XRD patterns of $0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ composite. From the Fig. 2, we can notice the evolution of the most intense peak, which reflects a broadening signature of composite formation. These results are similar to those reported by *E. Sellami et al.* [22].

Figure 2. Refined X-ray powder diffraction for $0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.95}\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{O}_3/0.5\text{Pr}_{0.67}\text{Ba}_{0.22}\text{Sr}_{0.11}\text{Mn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ composite.

The magnetic properties of the $\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}$ and $\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ manganites and their composite were characterized by the magnetization measurement vs. temperature in the range 5–350 K under a magnetic applied field of 0.05T. Fig. 3a shows the temperature dependence of the magnetization M (T) for both parent compounds. We clearly observed a sharp transition from paramagnetic to ferromagnetic state with decreasing temperature. The Curie temperature T_c was determined from dM/dT plots shown in the inset of Fig. 3a. It is found to be 135K for $\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}$ and 70 K for $\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$. The $M(T)$ curves of the $0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}/0.5\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ composite shown in Fig. 3b have two magnetic phase transitions which are in accordance with the $\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}$ and $\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ phase transition. At low temperatures when compared to the magnetization values of the $\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}$ and $\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ manganites, the magnetization value of the $0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}/0.5\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ composite is smaller than that of individual phases. This decrease caused by interactions between different magnetic phases with different T_c [23].

The variation of the magnetization as a function of magnetic applied field up to 5T at several temperatures was also measured for $0.5\text{PBSMF}_{0.05}/0.5\text{PBSFM}_{0.1}$ composites (Fig. 4). At low temperatures, the magnetization M increases sharply at low magnetic fields ($\mu_0H < 0.5$ T) and then saturates above 1 T. This result confirms the existence of ferromagnetic state at low temperatures for our composite.

In order to study the nature of magnetic phase transition, Banerjee criterion allows the determination of the order of the magnetic transition. It is based on the observation of the slope of the isotherm plots M^2 vs. μ_0H/M , a positive or a negative slope indicates a second order or first order transition, respectively [24]. The Arrott plots

M^2 vs. $\mu_0 H/M$ for the studied of the composite is displayed in Fig. 5. The Arrott curves have a positive slope which indicate that our composite undergoes a second order FM-PM phase transition.

Figure 3. $M(T)$ curves for **a)** Pbsmf_{0.05}, Pbsmf_{0.1} manganites and **b)** their composite at $\mu_0 H = 0.05$ T magnetic field. The inset is the dM/dT curves.

Figure 4. Isothermal magnetization for 0.5Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.11}Mn_{0.95}Fe_{0.05}O₃/0.5Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.1}Mn_{0.9}Fe_{0.1}O₃ composite measured at several temperatures.

Figure 5. H/M vs. M^2 curves of isotherms for 0.5Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.11}Mn_{0.95}Fe_{0.05}O₃/0.5Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.1}Mn_{0.9}Fe_{0.1}O₃ composite.

The magnetic entropy change (ΔS_M) of the 0.5 Pbsmf_{0.05} /0.5 Pbsmf_{0.1} composite, can be calculated from the isothermal magnetization measurements by applying to the formula given below [25]

$$|\Delta S_M| = \sum_i \frac{M_i - M_{i+1}}{T_{i+1} - T_i} \Delta H \quad (1)$$

Where M_i and M_{i+1} are the values of magnetization measured at T_i and T_{i+1} , respectively.

Figure 6 shows $|\Delta S_M|$ as a function of temperature under different magnetic applied field variations for the 0.5 Pbsmf_{0.05} /0.5 Pbsmf_{0.1} composite. As expected, $|\Delta S_M|$ exhibits two maximums around the transition temperatures, and the maximum ΔS_M value, increases with the amplitude of the magnetic applied field change. Under a magnetic applied field change of 5 T, it amounts $1.18 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for composite.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of the magnetic entropy change $|\Delta S_M|$ for the composite at different applied magnetic field.

The relative cooling power (RCP) for our composite, which expresses the cooling power of the magnetocaloric material, is determined by the following expression [26]

$$RCP(S) = -\Delta S_M^{max} \times \delta T_{FWHM} \quad (2)$$

δT_{FWHM} is the full-width at half maximum of the curve of ΔS_M . Under a magnetic applied field of 5T, the obtained values of RCP are found to be 175, 122 and 17.8 J/Kg for the PBSMF_{0.05}, PBSFM_{0.1} manganites and 0.5 PBSMF_{0.05} /0.5 PBSFM_{0.1} composite, respectively. The values display that RCP value of the composite is decreased by 10% when compared to those of PBSMF_{0.05}, PBSFM_{0.1} manganites. The decrease of The RCP can be explained by the increase in the number ratio of Fe³⁺-O-Fe³⁺ in the composite, which induces a weakening of the ferromagnetism. In addition, this evolution can be explained by the fact that the presence of iron weakens the double exchange interactions to the profit of the super exchange ones in the complex Fe³⁺-O-Mn³⁺[27-31]. We summarized in Table 1 the Curie temperature T_C, $-\Delta S_M^{max}$ and RCP values, in order to compare the results with those reported in literature [32-35].

Table 1. Comparison of magnetocaloric properties of our samples with the literature.

Materials	$\mu_0 H$ (T)	RCP (Jkg ⁻¹)	Ref.
PBSMF _{0.05}	5	175	This work
PBSFM _{0.1}	5	122	This work
0.5 PBSMF _{0.05} /0.5 PBSFM _{0.1}	5	17.8	This work
La _{0.67} Ca _{0.33} MnO ₃ /Fe ₃ O ₄	1	62.42	[32]
(La _{0.7} Ca _{0.3} MnO ₃) _{0.9} / (Co ₃ O ₄) _{0.1}	3	160	[33]
0.9La _{0.6} Ba _{0.2} Sr _{0.2} MnO ₃ /0.1Co ₂ O ₃	1	100.86	[34]
Gd	5	410	[35]

3. Conclusion

To conclude our scientific studies, the 0.5 PBSMF_{0.05} /0.5 PBSFM_{0.1} composite has been obtained by the mixture of the PBSMF_{0.05} and PBSFM_{0.1} samples in the mass ratio of 0.5:0.5 using the solid-state reaction. The magnetic and magnetocaloric properties have been studied by magnetization measurements. Magnetic measurements show that all samples exhibit a PM-FM transition with decreasing temperature. They exhibit a second-order ferromagnetic to paramagnetic phase transition. The magnetic phase transition of the materials has been determined as

second order by using Banerjee criterion. The $-\Delta S_M^{max}$ and RCP value for the 0.5 PBSMF_{0.05} /0.5 PBSFM_{0.1} composite under 5 T magnetic fields have been calculated as 1.18 10⁻³ J kg⁻¹K⁻¹ and 17.8 J/ kg respectively. Therefore, we indicate that the obtained results will represent attention of research for the development of magnetic refrigeration devices

Method

First of all, two manganites powder with compositions of Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.11}Mn_{0.95}Fe_{0.05}O₃ / Pr_{0.67}Ba_{0.22}Sr_{0.11}Mn_{0.9}Fe_{0.1}O₃ were elaborated using the solid-solid method at high temperature. Synthesis method is reported elsewhere [19] using stoichiometric amounts with higher purity than 99.9% of Pr₆O₁₁, BaO₂, SrO₂, MnO₂ and Fe₂O₃. Then, the appropriate amount of both samples with 50% of each was mixed and a homogenous powder was pressed into pellets and sintered at 1200 °C for 12h. The obtained samples were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction at room temperature in Panalytical X'PERT Pro diffractometer, using $\theta/2\theta$ Bragg-Brentano geometry with diffracted beam monochromatized CuK α radiation. The diffraction patterns were collected by steps of 0.017 over the angle range 10–70°. Structural analyses were checked by the Rietveld method using the FullProf program [20, 21]. Magnetization measurements were carried out using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) operating between 40 and 240K with an applied magnetic field up to 5T. Magnetocaloric effect (MCE) was estimated based on the magnetization measurements versus magnetic applied field up to 5T at several temperatures.

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Authors' contributions

K.S: Experimental parts, structural analyses and contribute to writing the manuscript. M.E: magnetization measurement and contribute to writing part of the manuscript

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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